

Decentralizing Authentication for Mobile Networks: Opportunities and Challenges in Web 3.0 Era

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Abstract—The mobile network connectivity relies heavily on the authentication service (mostly Authentication Server Function (AUSF) and Unified Data Management (UDM)), which handles authentication requests for both 3GPP access and untrusted non-3GPP access. It mainly allows users to access mobile operator services to enable communication between computers on different networks. However, the centralization of AUSF service in single location poses significant concerns for user security, privacy, and network accessibility. Small number of large AUSF servers increases the risks of data breaches and service disruptions in case of failures. There are also concerns about users’ digital sovereignty when it comes to hosting personal data. To address this issue, this paper proposes a blockchain network (BCN)-based self-sovereign identity (SSI) solution to distribute the centralization of authentication functionality in cellular networks and effectively increase users’ digital sovereignty. We also run a set of numerical simulations to evaluate the different credential times of the various metrics for a given number of requests (ranging from 50K to 100K). At the end of the paper, we explain the prospective constraints and viable remedies concerning the utilization of SSI for the advancement of security, privacy, trust, and interoperability within authentication frameworks in the Web 3.0 era.

Index Terms—self-sovereign identity, blockchain networks, Web 3.0, cellular networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Authentication Server Function (AUSF) is responsible for authentication and security-related tasks in 5G mobile networks [1]. Core functions of this service are (i) subscriber authentication, in which the AUSF verifies the identity of the subscriber or device attempting to access the 5G network, (ii) security key management, which manages the security keys used for encryption and decryption to ensure secure and reliable communication between the subscriber/device and the network, (iii) security context management, in which the AUSF manages the security context of the subscriber/device throughout the connection to the network, and finally, (iv) access authorization, which authorizes access to specific network

services based on the authentication and authorization status of the subscriber/device.

In existing mobile networks, centralising authentication services for mobile users across AUSF and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) introduces unavoidable security and availability risks, including compromised user privacy and the inability to authenticate users in the event of an outage or failure at one of the major providers. Consequently, serious concerns have been reported in the past in centralized systems such as in Home Subscriber Server (HSS) [2] which have disrupted communications services to a large number of subscribers¹. While mobility in mobile Internet scenarios can be administrated through distributed and dynamic mechanisms, security continues to emerge as a paramount concern for the key players of the network [3]. The reliance on large vendors to provide such a core IP network as AUSF creates dependability and digital sovereignty issues for subscribers, especially in light of regulations such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [4]. Decentralization with Blockchain Network (BCN) has been the focus of research in cellular networks in recent years. The authors in [5] proposed a secure blockchain-based authentication and key agreement for 5G networks (5GSBA) scheme to decentralize authentication functions from a central server to all base stations. It has been shown that decentralization with BCNs can also increase the difficulty of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks [6]. These efforts later translated into 5G-enabled IoT authentications [7] in which edge computing is used to decentralize the processing of authentication requests and eliminate the burden on authentication services and the central operations of the overall network.

A. 5G Registration

A user equipment (UE) needs to register with the network to receive services, to enable mobility tracking, and ensure reachability. Fig. 1 shows the 3GPP 5G Core Network (5GCN) authentication, which includes various functional units and the proposed BCN-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) authentication method, which is elaborated later in the paper. In the current 3GPP 5GCN system model, all gNodeBs in the 5G network are connected to nearby AMF servers. In the conventional 5G-AKA authentication process (in security architecture 3GPP TS 33.501), when a UE is within the coverage of gNodeBs, it sends an authentication request to the gNodeB, which then forwards it to the AMF. The AMF further

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¹Online: <https://urgentcomm.com/2022/09/20/reflections-on-recent-lte-outages/>, Available: July 2023

Fig. 1: Traditional 5G system architecture and authentication components and proposed BCN-based SSI for authentication and BCN for log processing.

forwards the request to the AUSF server. Subsequently, the AUSF retrieves the device secret keys from the Unified Data Management (UDM) server to continue with the authentication steps. Normally, one AUSF serves multiple AMFs across the 5G core network, and each AMF serves several nearby gNodeBs. Security vulnerabilities of AKA authentication process (3GPP TS 33.501 v0.7.0.) are previously identified and addressed [8]. The identified protocol vulnerability has the potential to allow an unauthorized actor lacking privileged network access to assume the identity of another user. The registration is performed in the following scenarios:

Initial Registration for Network Access: When an UE makes an initial connection to the 5G network, it goes through an initial registration process. During this process, the UE passes its identity and authentication credentials to the network to establish a secure connection. The network verifies the UE’s credentials, and after successful authentication, the UE is granted access to network services.

Mobility Registration Update During Handover: When the UE moves within the coverage area and switches from one base station (gNB) to another, a mobility handover occurs. To ensure seamless mobility and continuity of service, the UE performs a registration update with the new gNB. This update informs the network of the UE’s new location so that the network can route incoming traffic accordingly.

Registration Update During Network Reentry: If the UE temporarily loses network connectivity, such as when it enters an area with poor network coverage, it must rejoin the network as soon as it receives a signal again. In this scenario, the UE performs a registration procedure to re-establish its connection to the network.

Periodic Registration Update for Authentication Revalidation: Periodically, the UE authentication must be revalidated to ensure network security. This revalidation can be triggered based on specific time intervals or network conditions. The

UE goes through a re-registration process where its identity and credentials are confirmed to the network to continue to gain access to services.

Change in UE Identity: If the identity of the UE changes, such as the insertion of a new SIM card or an update of subscriber information, the UE must complete a registration process with the updated identity. This registration process is essential to ensure proper identification and continued provision of services.

Emergency Registration Update (for emergency services): In emergency situations, a dedicated registration procedure that allows UE to quickly and efficiently update its location information in the network. The main purpose of this update is to ensure that the emergency services can accurately and immediately locate and provide support for the UE in mission-critical circumstances.

B. Web 3.0 Enabled Telecommunication Infrastructure

The transition from Web 2.0 to Web 3.0 infrastructure represents a significant evolution in telecommunications [9]. Web 2.0 focused primarily on user-generated content and social interactions, while Web 3.0 enables a more decentralized, semantic, and intelligent Web [10]. Web 3.0 also enables the creation of new business models such as Decentralized Applications (DApps) and Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAOs) that foster innovation and user empowerment. The traditional Web 2.0 core network architecture consists of central servers responsible for handling user requests, processing data, and managing connections. However, the process of centralization introduces several constraints, including susceptibility to single points of failure, vulnerability to cyberattacks, and the risk of data breaches. The lack of transparency and control over data also raises concerns about user privacy and ownership. As Web 3.0 technologies continue to mature and gain traction, a shift toward more decentralized authentication approaches is also expected where trust and control are distributed among network participants rather than centralized entities.

In the current 5G authentication protocol, known as 5G-AKA, has significant vulnerabilities and places a great burden on the AUSF [11]. With the increasing number of connected devices in the future, the risk of Denial of Service (DoS) and DDoS attacks targeting the AUSF and other existing authentication entities in cellular networks becomes more prominent. Therefore, it is crucial to design a robust and resilient authentication system that effectively safeguards against DoS and DDoS attacks [12] to maintain continuous network operation and enhance the overall security and reliability of the next generation cellular network. In the era of decentralized and distributed technologies, the standards for centralized frameworks such as AUSF in cellular networks must be reevaluated. Decentralized authentication mechanisms can eliminate the need for third-party vendors, reducing potential single points of failure and creating a more resilient system. Users are not dependent on a centralized service that could be vulnerable to cyberattacks or service outages. In this context, alternative authentication mechanisms, such as the BCN-based SSI solution, may be of great interest and relevance.

Fig. 2: Evolution of core networks/cellular networks towards 6G in Web 3.0 era. Dotted lines depict the interconnects between the core networks.

C. The Roadmap for the Web 3.0 Transition

The process of Web 3.0 in cellular networks is illustrated in Fig. 2. The development is based on the basic example network architecture for a 6G communication system² with the new components Charging Function (CHF) and Control Plane Function (CPF). The newly added BCN-based SSI proposed in this paper is used as replacements for AUSF and UDM. In general, the use of BCN technology may offer the potential for decentralized authentication and identity management, eliminating reliance on a single centralized authority [13]. Authentication and authorization processes can be executed in a decentralized and trustless manner and provide more security and privacy by using Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT). The main idea is to decentralize the subscription repository from the UDM to all gNodeBs via BCN. This decentralization can empower gNodeBs to handle authentication tasks, thereby preventing DoS and DDoS attacks from compromising the quality-of-service (QoS) across the entire cellular network. Note that although a BCN may also introduce additional overhead during data synchronizations, it can offer the benefit of distributing authentication tasks, thereby reducing the risk of system overload. In this paper, we investigate how BCN-based SSI can help users create and manage their digital identities independently, storing their credentials and personal data on their devices or on decentralized networks. When authentication is required for network service access provided by Service Providers (SPs) or Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), users can present proof of their identity without revealing unnecessary personal information, reducing the risk of identity theft and ensuring a higher level of privacy.

II. SSI BLOCKCHAIN FOR AUTHENTICATION IN MOBILE NETWORKS

A. Integration Aspects for SSI

The adoption of decentralized authentication mechanisms is expected to significantly enhance security, reliability, privacy, and user control over personal data by eliminating single points of failure and reducing the risk of data manipulation. In our proposed system, we maintain the system model of Fig. 1, but decentralize the authentication entities. All gNodeBs connecting to the 5GCN act as verifiers and the subscribers' information resides in the BCN-based SSI. Hence, the AMF and

AUSF/UDM are no longer part of the authentication process which is now handled by BCN-based SSI. The UE possesses a unique Decentralized Identifier (DID) and is represented by a set of cryptographic keys and verifiable claims stored securely on the BCN. These verifiable claims can include personal information, certifications, or any other attributes that the UE wants to disclose for various interactions or transactions. When the UE needs to prove its identity to the gNodeB, it initiates an authentication request or identity verification process. Subsequently, for each authentication request, the gNodeB as verifier requests the UE to provide proof of certain attributes or claims from its DID. For example, the gNodeB may require the UE to prove its Permanent Equipment Identifier (International Mobile Station Equipment Identity (IMEI)), or Permanent Subscriber Identifier (International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI)). In response to the gNodeB's request, the UE selectively chooses relevant verifiable claims or attributes from its digital identity and presents them as verifiable credentials. These credentials are cryptographically signed and can be verified by anyone with access to the public keys stored on the BCN. The gNodeB, acting as the verifier, verifies the authenticity and validity of the presented verifiable credentials. It does so by validating the cryptographic signatures against the public keys stored on the BCN. Based on the verification results, the gNodeB may immediately grant or deny the UE's authentication request, without involving the AMF, AUSF, or UDM. Note that BCN is used as a method for SSI and allows SSI to have a distributed structure. We rely on the fact that devices in the mobile network can obtain their own and self-managed identities via SIM/e-SIM. The identity information provided with SSI is not just for authentication. The credentials can also help with other parameters (tariff, QoS, allowed services, etc.) in the user profile of participants.

B. Sequence Diagram for Authentication

The proposed approach puts the UE at the center of identity control, giving them greater autonomy over their personal data in the Web 3.0 era. It leverages a BCN-based SSI system that spans across all gNodeBs, serving as a distributed repository for subscriber data. Fig. 3 shows the sequence diagram of authentication with BCN-based SSI authentication in cellular networks. The protocol enables all connected gNodeBs to independently approve authentication requests from UEs, without requiring specific databases such as the AUSF and UDM entities. The proposed protocol consists of following four distinct phases:

Phase 1 – System Initialization: At this stage, when a new gNodeB becomes part of the cellular core network (CN), it goes through mutual authentication via an existing method, such as IPsec tunnels. Once authenticated, the gNodeB downloads the latest BCN from the cellular CN. When updates are received, the gNodeB adds new blocks to keep up with the latest information.

Phase 2 - UE Generation: In this phase, MNOs create the Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) and also send the relevant identification information to BCN. This phase ensures that only legitimate UEs with valid USIMs can access

²Online: <https://bit.ly/3YomjCn>, Available: August 2023

Fig. 3: Sequence Diagram of authentication with BCN-based SSI in cellular networks.

the mobile network, and the BCN serves as a tamper-proof record of the activation status and any subsequent revocations. **Phase 3 - gNodeB Broadcast:** After the initialization process, the gNodeBs proceed to broadcast their identities. Note that gNodeBs also have identities that are stored in the SSI BCN. The verifiers must be assigned to the system in a controlled manner with their IDs. In this case, it is possible to check whether a forged gNodeB has been added to the system as a verifier. This gives the UE the freedom to initiate authentication without having to respond to potentially forged identity requests from gNodeBs. Integration can be achieved using cryptographic methods in the UE authentication and gNodeB connection processes. This increases the security of the authentication process and enables a more reliable and controlled interaction between the UE and the gNodeBs.

Phase 4 - BCN-SSI Authentication: During this stage, as the UE initiates its boot-up process to commence authentication with the cellular network, a BCN-based SSI facilitates a two-way authentication between the UE and the gNodeB. This process also involves the authenticated recording of information utilizing blockchain technology on the backend.

C. Key SSI Entities

An overview of the key entities involved in BCN-based SSI is provided in Fig. 4. These entities include the SSI BCN, the issuer, the holder, and the verifier. In our context, the issuer represents a MNO and holds the power to generate and distribute digital credentials, known as verifiable credentials, to individuals or entities. These credentials consist of pertinent claims or attributes about the holder and are digitally signed by the issuer using their private key to ensure their authenticity and integrity. The holder, a UE in our case, receives and possesses the digital credentials issued by the issuer. The holder has complete control over their own credentials and can decide when and how to present them to verifiers. The credentials are securely stored in the holder’s digital wallet or enterprise data store, protected by the holder’s private key. The

holder has the ability to selectively share certain credentials or attributes with verifiers based on need or requirement, allowing the holder to maintain control over its own data. In our case, the verifier (more precisely, the gNodeB) plays the role of an entity responsible for verifying specific claims or attributes about another entity. If the verifier needs to verify the authenticity or validity of a claim made by the holder, the verifier can request the presentation of relevant credentials or attributes for verification purposes. The verifier relies on cryptographic signatures and the integrity of credentials. By validating the digital signatures and ensuring the integrity of the credentials with the issuer’s public key, the verifier can ensure that the credentials were issued by a trusted issuer and have not been tampered with.

D. Authentication Process

Smart contracts are self-executing contracts where the terms of the agreement are written directly into the code. In the context of our system, smart contracts play a central role in refining access policies and ensuring that only authenticated UEs are granted access to the RAN service. Most specifically, the smart contract on BCN-based SSI has exclusive invocation properties restricted to the issuer and the gNodeB controlled by that smart contract. The authentication process involves several important steps, each of which contributes to the secure and reliable authentication of users seeking access to RAN resources. In **step 1** of Fig. 4, when a holder (such as an UE) wishes to access the radio access network (RAN) service, they establish an authenticated channel with the issuer through BCN-based SSI. In **step 2**, the issuer issues a verifiable credential to the holder, including specific terms for the smart contract and the gNodeB to refine access policies. These terms may specify authorized time slots, specific parts of gNodeB, and more. In **step 3**, the holder presents the credentials to the gNodeB (verifier), which is then forwarded to BCN-based SSI. In **step 4**, the gNodeB verifies the ownership, authorship, and non-revocation of the credential. Additionally, the verifier checks the credential against a list of access policies set by the issuer. If authentication fails, the gNodeB denies RAN service requests from unauthenticated MNOs or refuses to collaborate with them. In **step 5**, the BCN-based SSI invokes the smart contract on the online BCN to check the gNodeB access policies using the presented credentials. Finally, in **step 6**, the smart contract informs the gNodeB about the authorization to write in the BCN. Upon successful authentication, the gNodeB initiates RAN services in collaboration with authenticated MNOs, and relevant logs are recorded in the BCN.

III. SIMULATIONS

A. Test Setup for DIM

We utilize the OpenStack platform and create two virtual machines. One virtual machine hosts a Representational State Transfer (REST) server responsible for generating requests to Hyperledger Indy, while the other virtual machine is configured with a container-based setup for the DID system. Hyperledger Indy serves as the BCN for managing DIDs, acting as the identity layer for our test setup. The DID

Fig. 4: Authentication steps within BCN-based SSI enabled system.

virtual machine is allocated 8 GB RAM, 4 vCPUs, and 40 GB disk space within OpenStack. During the installation of Hyperledger Indy, we set up the von network³, which enables the operation of container-based nodes. Specifically, four DID container nodes are created to serve as DID issuers. The REST API, implemented using the Flask framework, facilitates user requests to the BCN. To communicate with the BCN, we employ the DIDComm messaging protocol, an encrypted communication protocol developed as part of the Hyperledger Aries project⁴.

B. Credentials Results

Table I presents the results for the credential operations for SSI with a BCN-based system. Based on the experimental results presented in Table I, the following observations can be made regarding the performance of the credential operations: *The average credential presentation time*, which measures the time taken to present credentials to the verifier, ranges from 33 milliseconds (for 50,000 requests) to 39 milliseconds (for 100,000 requests). There is a slight increase in presentation time as the number of requests increases. *The average credential offer time*, which quantifies the time to generate and offer credentials to the holder, ranges from 525 milliseconds (for 50,000 requests) to 603 milliseconds (for 100,000 requests). Similar to presentation time, there is a slight increase with an increasing number of requests. *The average DIDComm connection creation time*, evaluating the time to establish a connection using the DIDComm protocol, ranges from 659 milliseconds (for 50,000 requests) to 736 milliseconds (for 100,000 requests). There is a moderate increase in connection

creation time as the number of requests increases. *The average DIDComm signing time*, measuring the time to sign messages using the DIDComm protocol, ranges from 64 milliseconds (for 50,000 requests) to 72 milliseconds (for 100,000 requests). The signing time remains relatively consistent across different numbers of requests. *The average DIDComm revoke credential time*, indicating the time to revoke a credential, ranges from 212 milliseconds (for 50,000 requests) to 277 milliseconds (for 100,000 requests). Similar to other metrics, there is a slight increase in revoke credential time as the number of requests increases. These results advocate for the slight latency cost for doubling the number of requests, providing an intuitive insight into the performance characteristics of the credential operations in the implemented system. Though most operations demonstrate efficient execution with average times within reasonable ranges, degradation in performance as the number of requests increases is mostly due to offering credentials and creating DIDComm connections.

C. Comparative Analysis

Table I and Table II can be used for a comparison of the credentialing operations performed and the AMF registration performance. When traditional authentication methods in cellular networks (e.g., AMF registration in [14]) is compared with the proposed BCN-based SSI method for cellular networks, we can observe distinct characteristics, advantages and limitations for each approach. Traditional authentication methods are characterized by centralized control that enables efficient data management and uniform authentication procedures across the network. This centralized approach simplifies the management of user data and provides a consistent security framework, but it also has significant drawbacks. Centralized systems have a single point of failure and can have problems with scalability and high network latency due to the dependency on a central server. In addition, they face the challenge of

³VON Network, Available: <https://github.com/bcgov/von-network>, Online: March 2023.

⁴Aries RFC 0005: DID Communication, Available: <https://bit.ly/3TKFUKG>, Online: March 2023.

Metric	Credentials Results
Presentation Time	33 ms (50,000 requests) 35 ms (75,000 requests) 39 ms (100,000 requests)
Offer Time	525 ms (50,000 requests) 565 ms (75,000 requests) 603 ms (100,000 requests)
DIDComm Connection Creation Time	659 ms (50,000 requests) 681 ms (75,000 requests) 736 ms (100,000 requests)
DIDComm Signing Time	64 ms (50,000 requests) 68 ms (75,000 requests) 72 ms (100,000 requests)
DIDComm Revoke Credential Time	212 ms (50,000 requests) 256 ms (75,000 requests) 277 ms (100,000 requests)

TABLE I: Average results for the proposed SSI BCN-based credential operations.

complying with data protection regulations and are not flexible enough to adapt to the evolution of authentication methods. The BCN-based SSI combines the advantages of SSI with the additional benefits of blockchain technology. This approach takes all the user control, privacy and security features of SSI while adding transparency, immutability and auditability through the blockchain's decentralized ledger. The use of distributed consensus mechanisms ensures the trust and integrity of the identity data stored in the blockchain. Despite these advantages, BCN-based SSI is not without its limitations. It is subject to the scalability and energy consumption limitations associated with blockchain technology. In addition, the complex consensus mechanisms and governance models require coordination between participants, and the adoption of BCN-based SSI may depend on the performance and availability of the underlying blockchain infrastructure.

From Table I and Table II, the BCN-based SSI system shows efficient credential operation times even under increased loads, demonstrating scalability and stability of performance. While traditional authentication methods improve with more CPU cores, they exhibit higher latency and fluctuations in registration times, especially at high request rates. This analysis highlights the potential benefits of BCN-based SSI systems in terms of lower latency and better scalability compared to traditional authentication methods. However, traditional methods can also achieve adequate performance with adequate resources, which underlines the importance of infrastructure for the efficiency of authentication.

IV. CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Challenges

The implementation of decentralized authentication mechanisms in cellular networks would require a careful consideration of various factors that require careful planning, optimization, and thorough cost-benefit analysis to ensure feasibility and efficiency. In decentralized identity management, ensuring zero trust across multiple distributed nodes and verifying the authenticity of each identity claim can be complex and resource intensive. Finding a balance between SSI and the benefits of a decentralized subsystem that implements the

Metric	Performance Results
Registration Time vs. CPU Cores	2000 ms (1 core) 1500 ms (4 cores) 1000 ms (8 cores) 500 ms (16 cores) 400 ms (32 cores)
Registration Time vs. Request Rate	2500 ms (100,000 requests/s) 2000 ms (20,000 requests/s) 1500 ms (2,000 requests/s) 1000 ms (200 requests/s) 500 ms (20 requests/s)
Average Registration Time vs. Total Requests	2 s (100 requests) 6 s (1000 requests) 10 s (10,000 requests)

TABLE II: AMF registration performance in traditional cellular authentication system [14].

authentication functions remains a challenge for telecommunications operators. In addition, the performance of existing blockchain systems with different consensus mechanisms can be a bottleneck for the implementations of AMF. Going forward, it is therefore imperative to implement strategies present in platforms such as Solana, Holochain, etc. to mitigate potential delays and utilise sharding mechanisms to reduce data transmission overhead. If these concepts are supplemented by layer 2 solutions, the speed of transactions per second can approach that of existing database systems. In terms of interoperability and cross-chain identity in a multi-blockchain environment, achieving zero trust across different BCNs while maintaining interoperability and consistent standards for identity verification can be complex. Compliance with the various privacy and data security regulations in different jurisdictions can be complex, especially in decentralized BCNs. In terms of scalability, maintaining real-time verification and validation for zero trust becomes more challenging as the number of users and verifiable credentials within the BCNs-based SSI solution increases. In addition, ensuring scalability without compromising security is a crucial aspect. In terms of privacy and data protection, while a blockchain offers inherent immutability and transparency, it can also expose certain data on the public ledger. A balance between transparency and data protection is important to protect sensitive identities and meet legal requirements.

B. Recommendations

A precise cost-benefit analysis for the implementation of BCN-based SSI is essential. DAOs and DApps can also play an important role in a BCN-based SSI solution by improving the overall functionality and control of the system and making it more decentralized, transparent and user-centric [15]. Both can be used in our context as follows: (i) DAOs can be used as governance structures for the BCN-based SSI solution, in which stakeholders, including UEs, MNOs, SPs and regulators can participate in decision-making. DApps also act as platforms on which trusted entities, such as government agencies can issue verifiable credentials for UEs. These DApps facilitate the process of identity verification and validation and ensure that the information stored in a UE's digital identity wallet is authentic and credible. Identity governance DApp can enable

DAO-based decision making for the BCN-based SSI solution. (ii) DAOs and DApps can empower UEs to have control over their digital identities. Users can become members of the DAO and have voting rights so that they can influence the rules for identity management. (iii) DAOs and DApp can establish mechanisms for identity verification and reputation systems. The DApp can track UE behavior, successful verifications, and overall trustworthiness, contributing to a UE's reputation score. (iv) DAOs can also manage a decentralized identity registry (as opposed to centralized systems such as UDM and AUSF) that securely stores hashed or encrypted user attributes. (v) DAOs can facilitate the attestation of identity claims by a network of validators (e.g. regulator bodies, legal authorities). (vi) DApp can function as a decentralized marketplace where UEs can select and choose from a variety of identity attestations offered by different validators.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Depending on the progress and adoption of Web 3.0 technologies in mobile networks, the exploration and adoption of decentralized authentication approaches will be important. The introduction of decentralized authentication mechanisms for mobile networks in the Web 3.0 era is intended to give users more options, increase security, and protect personal data by giving individuals control over their digital identities. In this paper, we considered the integration of the BCN-based SSI framework into the mobile network infrastructure to provide a more trusted, secure, and privacy-friendly authentication process for UEs. Numerical simulations were used to evaluate the performance of the proposed BCN-based SSI solution considering different metrics for a varying number of authentication requests. Finally, we discuss challenges and recommendations for using BCN-based SSI to improve authentication efficiency and scalability.

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